

The different manifestations of kinetic energy under electromagnetic and gravitational interactions

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Abstract: The different manifestations of kinetic energy under electromagnetic and gravitational interactions.

Key words: Kinetic energy, electromagnetic interaction, gravitational interaction.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1. (m_{am}) = [T]^2, \\ 2. \frac{(e_0)^2}{(4\pi)(\epsilon_0)(c)^2(a_0)} \frac{(m_{am})[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2}{(m_e)(c)^2} = [\Omega]^2, \\ 3. \frac{(m_{am})(e_0)}{(m_e)(R_\infty)(c)} = [T][\Omega], \\ 4. \frac{(m_{am})(c)^2(m_e)(c)^2}{(4\pi)(R_\infty)} = [T][\Omega], \\ 5. [T]/(c)^2 = \left[\frac{1}{(4\pi)(R_\infty)^2} \right]^2, \\ 6. [T] = \left[\frac{(c)}{(4\pi)(R_\infty)^2} \right]^2, \\ 7. [T] * 2(c)^2 = \frac{(m_e)(c)^2(m_e)(c)^2}{(m_e)}, \\ 8. [\Omega]/(c)^2 = \frac{(m_{am})}{(2\pi)(R_\infty)}, \\ 9. [\Omega] = \left[\frac{(e_0)}{(4\pi)(\epsilon_0)} \right]^2, \\ 10. [\Omega] * 2(c)^2 = \frac{(m_e)(c)^2(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2}{(m_e)}. \end{array} \right.$$
$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1. \left[\frac{(m_e)(r_{am})}{(4\pi)(r_{am})(r_{am})} \right]^2 = [U]^2, \\ 2. \left[\frac{(m_e)(r_e)}{(4\pi)(r_{am})(a_0)} \right]^2 = [N]^2, \\ 3. (2\pi)^2[\alpha_0]^2(2\pi)^2[\Omega]^2 = [U][N], \\ 4. (2\pi)^2[\Omega]^2 = [T][N], \\ 5. [U]/(c)^2 = \left[\frac{(2\pi)(a_0)}{(R_\infty)} \right]^2, \\ 6. [U] = \left[\frac{(2\pi)(a_0)(c)}{(R_\infty)} \right]^2, \\ 7. [U] * 2(c)^2 = \frac{(2\pi)^2(m_e)(c)^2(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2}{(m_e)}, \\ 8. [N]/(c)^2 = \frac{(m_{am})}{(2\pi)^2(R_\infty)(r_{am})(c)^2}, \\ 9. [N] = [(G_N)]^2, \\ 10. [N] * 2(c)^2 = \frac{(2\pi)^2(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2}{(m_e)}. \end{array} \right.$$

Reference: none.